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Environmental Factors And Academic Performance Of Secondary School Students In Etche Local Government Area Of Rivers State: Implication For Counselling

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of the study was to examine environmental factors and academic performance of secondary school students in Etche Local Government Area of Rivers State. The research design for the study was descriptive survey. One research question and one hypothesis guided the conduct of this study. The population of the study consisted of all the secondary school students in the area of study. The sample was three hundred (300) students. The sampling technique used was stratified random sampling. The instrument for the study is a structured questionnaire developed by the researcher titled “Environmental Factors Questionnaire (EFQ)”. Pearson product moment correlation was used to analyze the hypothesis. The result of the analysis was tested for statistical significance at the 0.05 alpha level. There is a positive high relationship between environmental factors and academic performance of students in Etche Local Government Area. Parents should provide their children/wards with conducive environment at and essential materials that will help them improve on their academic performance among others.

Keywords: Academic performance, environmental factors and students.

INTRODUCTION

Generally, in the whole world, particularly in Nigeria, education has been considered to be the corner stone for development. It forms the basis for literacy, skill acquisition, technological advancement and ability to harness human and material resources towards the achievement of societal goal (FRN, 2004). Education is very important in any given society. It is a process by which abilities and capabilities of individual are developed. These abilities might be physical abilities, emotional abilities, social abilities and intellectual abilities. It is the actualizing of human potential so that the individual can become something more than what he was before. According to Ugwuanyi (2003) education is the process by which society establishes to assist the young to learn and understand the heritage of the past, participate productively in the society and contribute meaningfully for the development of the society. Emeka (2008) citing Kneller (2000) sees education as a process by which any society through schools, colleges, universities and other institutions deliberately transmit knowledge, values and skills from one person to another.

The educational system is vital for every country in the world and Nigeria is no exception; a strong and effective education system can help boost the development of any country, as academic performance in Nigeria most especially at the secondary school level has been largely associated with many factors in literature. These include; school environment, lack of learning resources, psychological, social factors as

well as environmental factors (Adeagbe, 2004). Aremu and Sokan (2003) also reported tremendous academic failures among students and some have tried to find the reasons behind the alarming rate of failures. Thus, the problem of under-achievement of students at school has a long history in educational psychological research. Consequently, improving student academic achievement had long been an extremely complicated and vexing problem for school systems and education policy makers.

Environment, according to Webster's comprehensive dictionary, can be defined as the sum total of all surrounding of a living organism, including natural forces and other living things which provide conditions for development and growth as well as danger and damage. Environmental influence before now has not been considered as one of the factors that affect academic performance in secondary schools hence it has little or no attention in educational discourse and consideration. But, over the last decade, remarkable studies have indicated a correlation between the environment and academic performance of students.

Environment is the aggregate of all internal and external conditions affecting the existence, growth and welfare of organisms. It is an influence an individual came in contact with after the hereditary has been through the gene plasma. Anene (2005) explained that environment can be divided into physical, social and abstract. Physical environment is the objects or materials found in the home, school or community. It also includes the people like parents, siblings and peers (Anene, 2005). She also explained that the social environment is the social life, societies and club affecting the individual. Abstract environment is the reactions, feedback and the responses received on interactions with others. The author further explained that environment can also be classified as urban or rural environment. This therefore, entails the objects, materials, parents, siblings, peers and social life that exists in the home in which the student finds himself/herself. All the variables in the home that affect a person's existence, behavior and performance constitute the environmental factors.

Academic Performance on the other hand is the outcome of education; it is the extent to which a student, teacher or institution has achieved the educational goals. According to Bossaert and Doume (2011), academic achievement is commonly measured by examination or continuous assessment; however, there is a general agreement on how it is best tested. In some countries, the achievement of school is measured by the academic performance index. In Nigeria, academic performance is measured majorly by the student's performance in external examinations like WAEC Examinations both Senior and Junior, NECO examinations and JAMB examinations.

At this time, environmental factors have been the most persistent and thorny issues militating against secondary schools' ability to maintain existing services in Etche local government area in Rivers State. In order to achieve the goals of secondary education, the environment has to be conducive for learning. In fact, education thrives well only if there is good learning environment to assist learners to get the necessary information at each stage of learning. The environment constitutes an important aspect of the learning process. It creates the needed conditions for effectiveness of teaching and learning. Hence, it is pertinent to critically look at the environmental factors that influence academic performance of students, measures that can help, improve them and make some recommendations.

Statement of the problem

Good education does not happen by chance. It is a product of effective teaching and learning coupled with the effort of the teacher, the school, the students, parents and their various environments. Often a time the blames on the poor performance of students in school are shifted to the teachers and the school authorities.

Education is one other major means of providing an opportunity in life and helps one to belong to a suitable social class. It is widely recognized that many factors are involved in a child's academic performance. Such factors as parental education level, occupation, income, social class and type of parenthood for instance the socio-economic characteristics of the family play major role towards children's academic performance in school. They have a bearing also on the duration of his stay and achievement at school. The type of family and level of parents' education and their socio-economic status

influence the choice of school they place their children. Hill (2004) pointed out that socio economic status of parents has some influence on the academic performance of children.

Children from families with low socio-economic status are at a greater risk of hunger, homeless, sickness, physical and mental disabilities, violence, teen parenthood, family stress and educational failure. Students from low socio-economic background that encounter these environmental factors are four times more likely to have learning disabilities than students from high socio-economic background, while a combination of these environmental factors accelerate academic success. A student who has not eaten for days and has clothes that do not fit, cannot maintain focus in a classroom. Similarly, it is believed that factors such as malnutrition, lack of motivation in homes, spousal violence, and single parents as well as impoverished home environment affects the development of intellectual ability negatively (Mario, 2006). This means that students from low socio-economic backgrounds tend to be below or just an average in their intellectual development particularly when this phenomenon is accessed in terms of scores or tests. It is on this premise that this study was set out to examine environmental factors affecting the students' academic performances.

Aim and Purpose of the Study

The major purpose of the study was to investigate the relationship between environmental factors and academic performance of secondary school students in Etche local government area in Rivers State. The specific objective include:

1. To examine the influence of environmental factors on academic performance of students in Etche Local Government Area.

Research Questions

1. Do environmental factors influence the academic performance of students in Etche local government area?

Hypotheses

Ho1 There is no significant relationship between environmental factors and the academic performance of students in Etche local government area.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Concept of environment

Environment is the physical world inhabited by man, or the realm of nature untainted by man (human action), or the cultural milieu - the physical environment as modified by human action, (Ofomata, 2004). It could also be seen as things, around the child that he might perceive or that might have some effect on him. It can be viewed as all system of air, land, water and life that surround man. In other words, environment is the sum total of all the external conditions which may act upon an organism or community to influence its development or existence. For example, the surrounding air, light, moisture, temperature, wind, soil and other organisms. As for Monkhouse in Ofomata (2004) it is the whole sum of the surrounding external conditions within which an organism, a community or an object exists.

Chukwuemeka (2013) noted that environment play major role in the life of every individual whether a student, teacher, employer or employee. The challenge of education today is to offer experiences that provide students with opportunities to develop the understanding, skills, and attitudes necessary to become lifelong learners, capable of identifying and solving problems and dealing with change.

In order to achieve the goals of secondary education, the environment has to be conducive for learning. In fact, education thrives well only if there is good learning environment to assist learners to get the necessary information at each stage of learning. The environment constitutes an important aspect of the learning process. They create the needed conditions for effectiveness of teaching and learning. Hence, it is pertinent to critically look at the environmental factors that influence academic performance of students.

Empirical review

Relationship between Environmental Factors and Academic Performance of secondary school students

Onukwo (2004) in his note said that a conducive environment enhances a child's growth and development. Children feel happy in a peaceful and friendly environment where as schools sited in noisy urban streets are associated with deficits in mental concentration leading to student. Noise is anything that interferes with teaching/ learning process. Noise produces influence on children's information processing strategies, feelings of personal control as well as their level of arousal. Also, culture influences student's academic performance. The cultural environment influences aspiration because of culturally based explanations of behaviour tend to focus on the moral codes that operates within particular families, communities or groups. As culture has to do with beliefs, values, norms and socializations, research evidence has shown that the environment whether urban or rural also contributes to what a child learns and how it is being learned. Some communities have a history/tradition of formal education and modern education influences. Then while some are not so well equipped, the gadgets, resources, facilities in both types of community will influence the learning processes of the child. Students cannot single handedly achieve all their goals, so they must be equipped with adequate technological facilities such as textbooks, computers, visual and audio-visual aids, photographs and posters. Vikoo (2003) explained instructional material as anything that can be profitably employed to facilitate teaching learning process. Therefore, class without learning material can lead to students' poor academic performance, whether our measure of status is occupation of the parents, education or both of them. On the whole, the child's background affects the school success. Also, family stability has been found to exert serious effect on the child's education. Divorce, separation and single parenthood affect the children's academic performance. Technology influences the academic performance of students. Technology is of significant importance to the academic achievement of students. But instead of achieving academically, students turned it to be a cheating instrument. Most researchers concur that the incidence of academic misconduct in our middle schools and high school has increased significantly in recent years because of modern technology (Underwood & Szaba, 2003). Although educators and academics disagree on the root causes of this alarming behaviour, there is little disagreement that the accessibility of computers, the internet, and other electronic resources such as CD-ROM encyclopedias has made cheating quicker and easier for our current generation of Technology-Savvy teen. Cyber cheating" (meaning the use of technology tools in inappropriate ways for academic work. Because of this cheating on students, Futton (1997) persuasively argue that schools must change traditional approaches to learning in order to help today's students acquire the skill set required for succeeding in the work place of the future. This advanced skill will be achieved "through the learner's interactions with the content" "in the digital ages" and not through "the transmission of facts" (Futton 1997). Therefore, assessment tools should be designed in a way that knowledge and information are used in the adult world. Crownwell (2000) claim "many trend watchers think cheating is epidemic, usually beginning in, middle school and extending through college. Cheating is starting younger in elementary school, in fact by the time students hit middle and higher school, cheating is for many, like gym class and lunch period. Just part of the fabric of low things are what is changed is technology. It made cheating so easy (Schulte, 2002).

Thomas (2001:102) quoting Macabe (2001) asserted that "higher scholars are much more liable than college students to use the net to cheat, and computers have redefined younger kids concept of which constitutes cheating" McCabe also claims, based on his findings, that 15 to 20 percent of higher scholars bought or downloaded papers from one of many paper websites to submit as their work. Location/setting of school is one of the environmental factors that influence the academic performance of secondary school students. Onukwo (2004) in his note recorded that conducive environment enhances a child's growth and development. But schools sited near airports or at the heart of a city are always noisy and leads to deficits in mental concentration of students in such schools. School building is one of the school facilities that influence academic performance of students. The design of classrooms and its lighting also determine if students will perform well or not. Dunn (1985) said that students perform well in a bright environment than in a dark. Without light it is obvious that students may develop bad sight.

Sinofsky and Knirck (1981) found that color influences students' attitude, behaviours and learning. Color affects a students' attention span. Paints color in schools especially carefully planned color schemes positively affects academic achievement of students. A proper use of color in schools can convert an atmosphere that is depressing and monotonous into one that is pleasing, existing and stimulating. School climate can be a positive influence on the health of the learning environment or a significant barrier to the learner (Freibery, 1998:22). School climate research suggests that positive interpersonal relationships and optional learning opportunities for students in all demographic environments can increase achievement levels and reduces maladaptive behaviour.

Mohammed (2013) investigated the influence of school environment on academic performance from secondary schools in Mogadishu-Somalia. The study has three objectives which are: To examine the influence of school climate on academic performance at some selected secondary schools in Mogadishu-Somalia. To identify the effect discipline of teachers on academic performance at some selected secondary schools in Mogadishu-Somalia to investigate the relationship between school physical facilities and academic performance at some selected secondary schools in Mogadishu-Somalia. The researcher utilized convenient sampling to collect 80 questionnaires from secondary school teachers in Mogadishu, Somalia. These respondents were provided a questionnaire with four main construct which measuring school climate, discipline of teachers, school physical facilities as well as academic performance. the study found that academic performance (Dependent variable) had significant positive influence with three dimensions of independent variable. The result of regression analysis found that two constructs had statistically significant, positive, and straight effects with academic performance.

Chukwuma (2010) investigated the influence of school environment on academic achievement of students in Enugu State public secondary schools. The design of the study is descriptive while the population comprised principals and teachers in the education zone. The sample size for the study was 600 respondents while a researchers' self-developed questionnaire formed the instrument for data collection. Three experts validated the instrument and a cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient method was employed to ensure the reliability of the instrument. Four research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study; while student t-test statistics was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significant. A review of empirical studies was carried out to guide the researcher into previous studies in the area and also to provide the researcher with the theoretical base. A 29-item questionnaire was used to get information from the respondents. Based on the data collected and analyzed, the following results were obtained. That staff office, classroom spaces for teaching students and staff common room represented the major areas that to a great extent affect the academic achievement of students in public schools, with regard to buildings. It was also revealed that desks, current books and presence of library assistants constituted the areas of influence to the academic achievement of the students with regard to library services in the public secondary schools. Both the principals and teachers agreed that access to reading materials in the school, lack of facilities, and nearness to school and in sufficient qualified teachers very greatly affect the academic achievement of the students. Inadequate teaching materials were also noted as a major factor affecting the students' academic achievement. The two groups also shared common views in terms of the great influence of school health services, fencing of school for security and provision of power supply as important variable affecting the academic achievement of the students of public secondary schools. Based on the above, the researcher recommends that schools should be provided with functional libraries, equipped with current reading materials to help enhance both the students' academic achievement and the teachers' effectiveness in academic activities in the school.

Michael (2014) investigated some home environmental factors affecting the academic performance of students in Abia State, Nigeria. Survey research design was adopted for the study. Three research questions guided the study. The data were generated using structured questionnaire. A sample of 200 respondents from both junior and senior secondary school students and their parents were drawn through simple random sampling technique from secondary schools in the study area. Descriptive statistics example frequency, percentage and mean were used to analyze the data collected. The finding of the study revealed among others that none provision of adequate educational material by parents and

nonchalant attitudes of some parents towards the education of their children as well as the socio-economic status of the student's family, all affect the students' academic performance. Also revealed by the study are possible way of amelioration which among others includes giving proper orientation to the parents, on the implication and consequences of the type of family they may decide to adopt on the child's overall being especially the child's academic performance. Based on the findings it was recommended that parents no matter their busy schedule should make out time to sit down with their children or wards and check their children's academic work, direct them where necessary, discuss the academic problems of their children with their teachers or school guidance counselors so as to detect the student's problem early enough and tackle it before it affects the students.

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METHODOLOGY

The design of the study was a correlational survey. Nworgu (2006) defined correlation survey as a type of study that seeks to establish the relationship that exists between two or more variables. Usually, such studies indicate the direction and magnitude of the relationship between the variables. The population of this study will consist of all senior secondary school students in Etche local Government Area of Rivers State. Available statistics show that there are 6,000 senior secondary school students in Etche LGA of Rivers State (Rivers State Education Board, 2015). Simple random sampling technique was used in order to give every student equal chance of being selected for the study. A sample of 300 students was used for the study. This sample was randomly drawn from a population of 2,198 teachers. The instrument for the study was a structured questionnaire developed by the researcher. The questionnaire titled "Environmental Factors and Students Academic Performance Questionnaire (EFSFSAPQ) was divided into two parts. Part A elicits the demographic data of the respondents while part B with 29 items to be responded to. The instrument is with the four points modified Likert scale of Strongly Agreed (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), Strongly Disagree (SD) weighted as 4,3,2,1, point respectively.

To ensure the validity of the instrument, the instrument was given to my supervisor and two other lecturers in the department of measurement and evaluation to determine the suitability of the constituent items of the instrument. The instrument was later modified to integrate all the suggestions made by the supervisor and the experts. Hence, the instrument underwent face and content validity. In order to determine the reliability of the instrument, the researcher adopted the test-re-test method. The researcher administered 20 copies of the instrument to 20 respondents that was not included in the sample for this study. Cronbach Alpha Statistical analysis was be used to determine the internal consistency coefficient of the instrument. The researcher together with the assistance of two research assistants will use Direct Delivery method to administer the questionnaire to the teachers. The research assistants will be educated by the researcher on the purpose of the study and how to administer the questionnaire. The researcher and research assistants will administer the questionnaire to the respondents and collect it back immediately on completion. The use for research Assistants is to facilitate quick distribution and retrieval of the questionnaire from the respondents. Mean and Standard deviation will be use to answer research questions. While the hypotheses will be tested at 0.05 level of significance using the independent t-test.

ANALYSIS OF DATA

Research Question 1: *Do environmental factors influence the academic performance of students in Etche local government area?*

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between environmental factors and the academic performance of students in Etche local government area.

Table 4.1: *Pearson Product Moment correlation on the relationship between environmental factors and the academic performance of students in Etche local government area.*

Category	N	R	Sig.	Remarks
environmental factors	180	0.896	0.000	Significant
academic performance				

Table 4.1 revealed that the r value is 0.896 which depicts a positive high relationship between environmental factors and academic performance of students in Etche local government area. In order to test the null hypothesis, significant probability value of 0.000 is subjected to the critical probability value of 0.05. Since the significant probability value is less than the critical probability value of 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected. By implication, there is a statistical significant relationship between environmental factors and academic performance of students in Etche local government area.

DISCUSSION

The finding of the study revealed that environmental factors influence the academic performance of students in Etche local government area. There is a positive high relationship between environmental factors and academic performance of students in Etche local government area. The finding is in line with Monkhouse, in Ofomata (2004), it is the whole sum of the surrounding external conditions within which an organism, a community or an object exists. Chukwumeka (2013), noted that environment play major role in the life of every individual whether a student, teacher, employer or employee. The challenge of education today is to offer experiences that provide students with opportunities to develop the understanding, skills, and attitudes necessary to become lifelong learners, capable of identifying and solving problems and dealing with change. In order to achieve the goals of secondary education, the environment has to be conducive for learning. In fact, education thrives well only if there is good learning environment to assist learners to get the necessary information at each stage of learning. The environment constitutes an important aspect of the learning process. They create the needed conditions for effectiveness of teaching and learning.

CONCLUSION

The study focused on examining the environmental factors that influence the academic performance of secondary school students in Etche local government area in Rivers State. The finding of the study revealed that environmental factors influence the academic performance of students in Etche Local Government Area. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between environmental factors and academic performance of students in Etched Local Government Area.

Implication for Counseling

Guidance counsellors as professionals should help to guide students in their right path morally and academically. They should be seen to be doing a lot for students in terms of getting to know the students better and applying their professional skills to help them. The guidance professionals must get hold of studies like this one to be able to learn more about their students and apply the finding and recommendation practically. Students should be more alert to their studies and beware of negative influences from peers. Policy makers need studies like this one to help them make sound educational

policies, government or representatives must provide the needed facilities and environment conducive for learning in schools.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the finding of this study, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Parents should provide their children/wards with conducive environment and essential materials that will help them improve on their academic performance.
- ii. The principals of post primary schools in the State should discuss/educate parents on the importance of providing adequate learning materials as well as creating learning environments in their homes to their children. This could be discussed in the Parent/Teachers Association meetings.
- iii. Literate parents/busy parents should squeeze out time out of their tight schedules to stay with their children and check their academic progress.
- iv. Parents should make out time to reach out with their children's teachers from time to time to update them with their children's academic progress. This will help identify the student's academic problems so as to handle it promptly before it affects the students.

REFERENCES

- Adeagbe, T. T. (2004). Effective communication language teaching method, parent supportiveness and gender in learning outcomes and attitude in Yoruba reading comprehension: PhD thesis. Ibadan: University of Ibadan.
- Anene G. U. (2005). Home environment and the academic performance of a child, *Journal of Home Economics Research*, Vol. 6 (1), pp. 99-100.
- Bossaert G., Doumen S., Bugse E. & Verschueren K. (2011). Predicting Student's Academic Achievement after the Transition to First Grade: A Two –Year Longitudinal Study, *Journal of Applied Development Psychology*, Vol. 32, pp.47-57.
- Brown, G. L. (2006). Parent and community involvement: A Casebook for exploring Diversity. New Jersey: Pearson Education Inc., pp 149-159.
- Chukwuemeka, O. (2013). Environmental influence on academic performance of secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 14, 12.
- Cromwell, S. (2000). What can we do to curb student cheating? *Education world*, January 24, 2004. (Retrieved online July 8, 2017 from [http://pareonline.net/getvn.asp?v=9 & n=9](http://pareonline.net/getvn.asp?v=9&n=9)).
- Farhent, N. (2001). Sociology, psychology determination of academic achievement of children in Pakistan.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2004). National policy on education (4thed). Lagos: Nigerian Educational Research & Development Council.
- Fraser, E. (1985). *School and home*: London: University of London press.
- Freiberg, H. J. (Ed.). (1998). *School climate: measuring, improving and sustaining healthy learning environments*. Philadelphia, PA: Falmer Press.
- Ganai, M.Y. & Muhammad, A.M. (2013). Comparative study on adjustment and academic performance of college students. *Journal of Educational Research and Essays* 1(1), 5-8.
- Ogunboyede, M.O. (2001). Women academic achievement: A case study of senior secondary school agricultural science students in Ekiti state Nigeria. *Journal of Educational Research* (1), 12-20.
- Penny, M. (2001). Understanding children's challenging behaviour, why try to influence or change behaviour for a variety of purposes. Richmond: Nelson.
- Ugwuanyi, T. (2013). Grappling with the issue of homosexuality: perceptions, attitudes, and beliefs among high school students in Kenya. *Journal of Psychology Research and Behaviour Management*, 3(2), 253-262.
- Vikoo, B. (2003). *Learning theories and instructional processes*. Owerri: Springfield Publishers.